

Sadvritta in Ayurveda – Code of Conduct for Healthy Lifestyle

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Abstract:- Health is not a single entity, it is multidimensional which includes physical, mental, social and spiritual aspect of life. These facets are interrelated and interconnected to each other. Any deviation in any of these facets will reflect in all the four aspects. Hence to achieve normalcy, it is necessary to keep all the four aspects of life in equilibrium. Sadvritta is one of the principles of Ayurveda which keeps all the aspects of health in equilibrium. The concept of sadvritta is dispersed extensively in all the Ayurvedic classics. The present review article is intended to focus on sadvritta related to physical, mental, social and spiritual health of the individual which may improve the quality of living.

Keywords:- Health, Sadvritta, Quality of life.

I. INTRODUCTION

The word sadvritta is made up of two words 'sad' which means right or good and 'vritta' which refers to acharana or regimen. Acharya Chakrapani defines sadvritta as being in the company of righteous person. Acharya Vagbhata defines sadvritta as compassion towards all the living beings, granting of gifts, controlling the activities of body, mind and speech, feeling of selfishness in the interest of others.

In Ayurveda, health is defined as the state of equilibrium of dosha, agni, dhatu and malakriya, prasannatha of amta, indriya and mana. One desirous of his own wellbeing should adhere to good regimens with proper care. Ayurveda explains sadvritta related to various aspects of health which can be classified as physical conduct (sharirikasadvritta), mental conduct (manasikasadvritta), social conduct (samajikasadvritta), moral conduct (dharmikasadvritta) and ethical conduct (vyavaharikasadvritta).

Sharirikasadvritta: It refers to good regimens related to physical health. Acharya Charaka has elaborated the measures which aids in achieving good physical health.

Following dinacharya which starts from getting up in brahmimuhurtha, keeping feet, excretory passages clean and taking bath daily, wearing a good cloth, avoiding forceful initiation of urges, one should wear footwear and should hold an umbrella while walking.

Sadvritta related ahara – consuming food only after the digestion of previously taken food and when there is proper hunger, consuming food by considering the aharavidhividhana and ashtaaharavidhivisheshayathana. Freshly prepared food should be consumed in a clean and calm place and water should be consumed in between the meals. A minimum of hundred steps should be walked after consuming food, avoiding day sleep, physical exertion after food.

Manasikasadvritta: It refers to conducts which helps to possess good mental health. One should be virtuous, kind and mild nature, one should always be happy, one should always forget the reasons of anger and hatred, avoid excessive utilization, improper utilization and poor utilization of sense organs, avoid thinking bad for others and having too much proud. Acharya Vagbhata says to avoid dashavidha papa karma pertaining to body, mind and manas which helps in achieving good mental health.

Samajikasadvritta: It refers to good conducts which are beneficial in improving the social health. Avoiding dashavidhapapakarma can also help in maintaining good social health. One should respect teachers, elders and parents. One should always help the needy people, dependent one. Avoid misbehaving in the public.

Dharmikasadvritta: It refers to the good conducts which promotes spiritual health. Without being clean one should not worship the fire by offering cow ghee, akshatha, tila, kushagrass and sarshapa. These measure are told to keep one's sense organs in control so that the individual is able to understand the satya and mithya of the world then he will be able to pursue the purpose of life. This is how one can achieve the spiritual health.

Vyavaharikasadvritta: It refers to ethical conducts. One can lead a successful life by following the ethics in life. One should not tell lies, should not long for others wives and property, one should not disclose others defects, one should not disclose others secrets, one should avoid the company of mean minded and crooked persons, one should not possess enmity with good men or be friends with bad ones. One should not indulge in sexual intercourse with women who has no interest in it, sexual act should not be done in sandhyakala, and one should not neglect dependents. Following these ethics will lead to a meaningful healthy life.

II. ROLE OF SADVRITTA IN CONTROL AND PREVENTION OF DISEASES:

Chaukhamba Sanskrit sansthan; 2016. Sutra sthana, 2nd Chapter.

Covering the mouth and nose while sneezing, coughing, laughing can protect the individual from droplet infection. Discharging of urine and fecal matter in the direction of wind is prohibited as it may lead to water contamination. Cohabitation with the unknown women, unhygienic women, more than one women can lead to sexually transmitted diseases like HIV, Hepatitis B etc. Chatradharana can help the individual against mist, fog, rain, intense sunlight. Padukadharana can prevent the hookworm infestation, other injuries and small insects bite. Dandadharana can help the individual from attack of animals like dog which can prevent from rabies. Walking on the heap of ash is contraindicated as it may cause pneumoconiosis.

III. DISCUSSION

As the origin of disease is psychosomatic, following sadvritta referring to good conducts not only helps in treating diseases but also promotes good physical and mental health. The sharirikasadvritta helps in detoxifying the physical body externally as well as internally. There by helps in proper absorption of nutrients and leads to proper nourishment of the body. The manasikasadvritta helps to have control over sense organs so that the individual will be able to make judicious decisions at appropriate time. The samajikasadvritta and vyavaharikasadvritta helps to build confidence in one self to cop up with the challenges of society and lead a better quality life. Dharmikasadvritta helps the individual to become stronger from within by understanding purpose of life.

IV. CONCLUSION

Ayurveda being a holistic science of life, advocates the healthy lifestyle to lead a better quality life. By following the sadvritta that is the code of good conducts, one can prevent the occurrence of diseases through promotion of positive health.

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